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5 **Do Sustainable Community Rating Systems address**
6 **resilience?**

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8 **Keywords:** Community Rating Systems; Disaster Risk; Resilience; Sendai Framework;
9 Sustainable Development Goals; Urban Development

10 **Abstract** Extensive damages and numerous casualties are produced by natural disasters
11 and hazards in urban areas. Hence, the absorption, recovery and adaptation to them
12 through resilience are highly necessary to ensure operation and enhancement of urban
13 systems. The significance of urbanization led to launch some tools such as BREEAM
14 Communities, CASBEE for Urban Development, DNGB Urban Districts, Green Star
15 Communities, LEED for Neighbourhood Development or STAR Community to promote
16 sustainable development in communities and cities. After selecting the most relevant
17 community rating systems, this research determined their adequacy to handle urban chal-
18 lenges by benchmarking them against the major international efforts and some relevant
19 resilience assessment tools extracted from the study of eight global frameworks. Thus,
20 the Sendai Framework and the 2030 Agenda represented the former, whilst the latter con-
21 sidered the City Resilience Index and the City Resilience Profiling Tool. The findings of
22 this investigation revealed that the indicators of STAR Community and BREEAM Com-
23 munities reflected the highest level of correspondence with the resilience assessment
24 frameworks. However, the existence of prominent gaps in all the screened community
25 rating systems suggests the need for developing a new tool involving both resilience and
26 sustainability.

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28 **1. Introduction**

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30 Urbanization can promote sustainable development, but also can increase vulnerabil-
31 ities and risk derived from urban spatial constraints, socio-economic inequalities, envi-
32 ronmental issues and inadequacy of institutions. Furthermore, urban areas concentrate
33 most damages and losses from disasters, mainly due to the combination of the low-quality
34 of informal settlements and unplanned urbanization, which occurs in hazardous and mar-
35 ginal areas such as floodplains, coastlines or zones of higher seismic risk.

36 Disaster risk represents the potential of natural and human-caused hazards to produce
37 negative impacts on the community, involving people, prosperity and planet assets (Pel-
38 licher et al., 2016), namely the sustainable Triple Bottom Line (TBL) (Elkington, 1997).
39 These disasters reflect the close relationship between natural and human systems and in-
40 frastructure. Since a city can be considered as a variety of interrelated systems (Short,
41 2006) made of different physical and social components (Rus et al., 2018), resilient com-
42 munities require that the physical socio-economic, governance and environmental sys-
43 tems work and function together (Missimer et al., 2007).

44 The term resilience can refer to a broad spectrum of elements (UNISDR, 2017a),
45 adopting multiple definitions that have evolved over time (Salas and Yepes, 2018). Whilst
46 some people describe resilience as the ability of a system to show strength under adversity
47 and bounce back after some hazard, other individuals emphasized the ability to prepare
48 and plan for, absorb, recover from and adapt to adverse events (NAS, 2012). More accu-
49 rately, this last meaning covers the two-fold component involving risk and resilience. The

50 capacity of the former to withstand and respond to hazards features, as well as the adap-
51 tation and recovery of the latter (Linkov et al., 2018).

52 Since the approval of the Yokohama Strategy and Plan of Action for a Safer World in
53 1994 (UNISDR, 1994), some global actions were developed in the field of resilience until
54 the adoption of the present Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030
55 (UNISDR, 2015). Different tools have been created for evaluating the resilience of sys-
56 tems that can be implemented in communities, such as the Resilience Matrix (Fox-Lent
57 et al., 2015), some frameworks developed by the US National Institute of Standards and
58 Technology (NIST, 2018) or multiple urban resilience assessment tools, inter alia, the
59 City Resilience Index (Arup, 2015), the City Resilience Profiling Tool (UN-Habitat,
60 2012) or the Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities (UNISDR, 2017b). Furthermore,
61 innovative studies aimed at correlating the urban environment to resilience/security have
62 also been developed recently. Some of the most relevant ones include a street crime pre-
63 diction model (Lee et al., 2017), the Security Rating Index (Shach-Pinsly, 2019) or the
64 Resilient, Sustainable, Safe and Inclusive Community Rating System (Diaz-Sarachaga
65 and Jato-Espino, 2019).

66 The enhancement of life condition taking into account the social, economic and envi-
67 ronmental dimensions of the TBL for present and future generations is the aim of sustain-
68 ability (Collier et al., 2013). The international community launched different global initi-
69 atives to address sustainable development issues, being the Agenda 21 adopted in the
70 Earth Summit held in Rio in 1992 the starting point (UNCED, 1992). At present, the 2030
71 Agenda for Sustainable Development (UN-Habitat, 2015) has paved the way for achiev-
72 ing 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (SDSN, 2015) before the end of 2030.
73 More specifically, the SDG#11 (“Sustainable Cities and Communities”) intends to trans-
74 form cities into safer and more inclusive, resilient and sustainable places for living.

75 The growing significance of the concept of green building as a response to primarily
76 minimize resource consumption and harmful effects on human health and the environ-
77 ment led to the launching of diverse rating systems to gauge the sustainability of buildings
78 (Cole, 2013). Then, these systems evolved into new frameworks for the assessment of
79 neighborhoods and communities (Berardi, 2013), such as LEED for Neighbourhood De-
80 velopment (LEED ND), BREEAM Communities, CASBEE for Urban Development
81 (CASBEE-UD), STAR Community, DGNB Urban Districts (DGNB UD) and Green Star
82 Communities, among others.

83 Sustainability and resilience share similarities in what concerns the improvement the
84 conditions of individuals and communities, but have also some differences. Whilst the
85 former is mainly focused on the 3 P’s (Planet, Prosperity and Planet), the latter deals with
86 the response of systems characterized by the 4 R’s (Robustness, Redundancy, Resource-
87 fulness and Rapidity) (Rus et al., 2018). In this context, where resilience plays a leading

88 role in sustainable development, this research aimed at analyzing major sustainable com-
 89 munity rating systems to determine their contribution to the assessment of resilience in
 90 urban areas.

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92 2. Materials and methods

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94 As shown in Figure 1, this investigation encompassed two different stages, namely
 95 the selection and comparative assessment of the components employed in the study. In
 96 next subsections, a brief analysis of the most relevant community rating systems was un-
 97 dertaken to determine which of them should be considered, whilst current global initia-
 98 tives adopted by the international community in the field of resilience were also recog-
 99 nized. Furthermore, several resilience frameworks were examined to shortlist those to be
 100 used in the assessment conducted in Section 3.

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Figure 1. Research methodology for the evaluation of sustainable community rating systems in terms of resilience

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106 2.1. Selection of sustainable community rating systems

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During the last two decades, around a score of third-party assessment frameworks were developed to appraise the sustainability performance of a given community against a set of criteria, such as Envirodevelopment (Australia), One Planet (UK), BCA Green Mark for District (Singapore), IGBC Green Townships (India), GSAS/QSAS (Qatar), Pearl Community (UAE), Neighbourhood Sustainability Framework (New Zealand), EcoDistricts (USA) and Ecocity (EU). Most of them are bespoke tools that reflect specificities of the regions and countries where they were built, with little or no implementation beyond their borders and minor international relevance. On the contrary, BREEAM Communities, LEED for Neighbourhood Development, DGNB Urban Districts, CASBEE for Urban Development, STAR Communities and Green Star Communities reached wide international dissemination.

119 The British Building Research Establishment (BRE) presented a pioneer third party
120 certification scheme in 2008 to appraise social, economic and environmental impacts at
121 the neighbourhood or larger scales, called BREEAM Communities. It includes 5 technical
122 categories, namely Governance, Land Use & Ecology, Resources & Energy, Social &
123 Economic Wellbeing and Transport & Movement, comprising 40 graded indicators that
124 can reach up to 126 points. Some of them are mandatory, such as Consultation Plan
125 (GO01), Ecology Strategy (LE01) or Flood Risk Assessment (SE03), among others.
126 Moreover, an additional innovation category rewards projects whose performance is be-
127 yond the levels of the system. Although BREEAM Communities was originally con-
128 ceived to be applied to projects in the United Kingdom, it could also be used in other
129 countries after a bespoke assessment process to ensure its appropriateness for the context
130 where the project is located. Some national scheme operators are licensed by the BRE in
131 some countries to conduct the bespoke process, which can reflect some amendments and
132 additions to the BREEAM standard criteria. Furthermore, all BREEAM programs follow
133 the same standard BREEAM certification process. This framework differentiates 6 rating
134 benchmark levels for final certificates: outstanding, excellent, very good, good, pass and
135 unclassified ([BREEAM, 2012](#)).

136 LEED v4 ND rates projects according to five categories: Smart Location and Linkage,
137 Neighbourhood Pattern and Design, Green Infrastructure & Buildings, Innovation & De-
138 sign Process and Regional Priority. Overall, it covers 44 credits and 12 critical prerequi-
139 sites that are required to achieve any of the four levels of certification according to the
140 points earned in relation to the total score of 100 points: Certified, Silver, Gold and Plat-
141 inum ([USGBC, 2018](#)). A LEED v4.1 for Cities and Communities draft was released in
142 December 2018, covering 8 categories and 35 prerequisites & credits, but it is not opera-
143 tional yet.

144 The DGNB UD 2016 version requires a minimum size of 2 hectares as a gross site
145 area (GSA), comprising infrastructure, buildings and public spaces in the district. Envi-
146 ronmental, Economic, Sociocultural & Functional, Technical and Process are its 5 cate-
147 gories, which include 30 indicators to be scored. A maximum of 10 points is granted for
148 reaching the target values assigned to the indicators. According to the total performance
149 index rate, the project can achieve different levels of certification: Bronze, Silver, Gold
150 and Platinum ([DGNB, 2016](#)).

151 With the support of the Japanese Government, the Research Committee for the Com-
152 prehensive Assessment System for Built Environment Efficiency (CASBEE) was estab-
153 lished in 2001 to develop some methods to evaluate the environmental performance of
154 buildings. Hence, CASBEE-UD was released in 2006 as an application of the CASBEE
155 tools at block/zone scales covering several hectares ([CASBEE, 2014](#)). The current 2014
156 version encompasses 88 indicators grouped into two main categories: QUD (“Environ-
157 mental Quality of Urban Development”) and LUD (“Environment Load of Urban Devel-
158 opment”), which are applied within and outside the site boundaries, respectively. Whilst

159 the former assesses three concerned categories, namely Environment, Society and Econ-
160 omy, the latter measures the reduction of environmental load in traffic, building and
161 greening sectors. The Built Environment Efficiency (BEE) indicator, calculated as the
162 quotient of Q_{UD} over L_{UD}, ranks projects according to five grades: Superior (S), Very
163 Good (A), Good (B+), Slightly Poor (B-) and Poor (C) (IBEC, 2014).

164 STAR Community arose in 2012 as the result of a consensus-based process conducted
165 in the United States, integrating diverse economic, environmental and social aspects of
166 sustainability focused on the local context and community needs. The framework is or-
167 ganized in 7 goal areas covering Built environment, Climate & Energy, Economy & Jobs,
168 Education, Arts & Community, Equity & Empowerment, Health & Safety and Natural
169 Systems. Each category contains several credits that are scored based on their accom-
170 plishment. The Innovation & Process category can provide additional points to reward
171 projects with an outstanding performance. The present version 2.0, released in 2016,
172 aligns the framework with recent global sustainability initiatives, such as the SDGs or the
173 standard ISO 37120:2014 (“Sustainable development of communities – Indicators for city
174 services and quality of life”) (STAR, 2016). Three certification levels are provided by the
175 rating system according to the range of points achieved by communities: Certified 3-
176 STAR Community, Certified 4-STAR Community and Certified 5-STAR Community.

177 The Green Star Communities pilot version was launched in 2012 by the Green Build-
178 ing Council of Australia (GBCA), being updated in September 2016. This framework
179 aimed at supporting Australian local governments to promote the planning, design and
180 construction of communities focused on the integration of sustainable actions and the
181 stakeholder participation by assessing five aspects, namely Governance, Liveability, Eco-
182 nomic Prosperity, Environment and Innovation, through 33 indicators (GBCA, 2016).
183 Three levels of certification are considered according to the score achieved: 4 Star Green
184 Star, 5 Star Green Star and 6 Star Green Star. Table 1 summarizes the main characteristics
185 of these six prominent rating systems.

Table 1. Characteristics of the frameworks with the highest international outreach (BREEAM, 2012; CASBEE, 2014; DGNB, 2016; GBCA, 2016; STAR, 2016; USGBC, 2018)

Rating System	Country	Current Version	Categories	Indicators/ Credits	Total Certified Projects	Foreign Certified Projects	Development Size
DGNB UD	Germany	2016	5	30	14	6	> 2 hectares (GSA)
LEED v4 ND	USA	2018	5	56	460	131	2 buildings – 1,500 acres
CASBEE-UD	Japan	2014	2	88	6	0	1 block scale - several hectares
BREEAM Communities	United Kingdom	2012	6	40	51	26	Large scale
STAR Community	USA	2016	8	49	74	0	Municipal level
Green Star Communities	Australia	2016	5	33	42	0	> block with at least 300 dwellings

189 Relevancy, implementation outside their countries of origin and exclusivity in terms
 190 of being community-oriented were the criteria established to select the systems to be
 191 deemed in the study. The assessment tools with the highest amount of certified projects
 192 are LEED v4 ND, STAR Community, BREEAM Communities and Green Star Commu-
 193 nities. Among them, LEED v4 ND and BREEAM Communities served to certify a sig-
 194 nificant number of developments outside their countries of origin. However, the incorpo-
 195 ration of LEED v4 ND to the research was discarded because its lower threshold of ap-
 196 plication (“at least two habitable buildings”) seriously questions the adequacy of this tool
 197 for appraising communities whose size ranges from neighbourhood to county scales. By
 198 contrast, STAR Community was principally designed to assessing communities at the
 199 municipal level without being part of a certification program focused on buildings. Whilst
 200 most frameworks are employed by private stakeholders to achieve sustainable recogni-
 201 tion, STAR Community and Green Star Communities support a high number of local
 202 governments in the assessment of urban communities. Thus, BREEAM Communities,
 203 STAR Community and Green Star Communities met the selection criteria to be consid-
 204 ered in this study.

205 As reflected in [Table 2](#), the organization of the three selected frameworks varies sig-
 206 nificantly. Whilst BREEAM and STAR present several thematic groups on main sustain-
 207 ability issues, Green Star associates each category to social, economic, environmental and
 208 governance dimensions. STAR and Green Star revealed a balanced treatment of the four
 209 sustainability pillars, but BREEAM neglected economic and environmental matters. Fur-
 210 thermore, the three shortlisted tools highly consider the key role of the spatial/urban lo-
 211 cation aspect, which mainly influences the recovery capability of urban areas after the
 212 occurrence of disasters. Several categories focus on this aspect, such as Governance and
 213 Land Use & Ecology (BREEAM), Built Environment, Health & Safety and Natural Sys-
 214 tems (STAR) and Governance and Environment (Green Star). High performance projects
 215 are rewarded by an Innovation section in all tools.

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Table 2. Categories included in the three selected community rating systems ([BREEAM, 2012](#); [GBCA, 2016](#); [STAR, 2016](#))

BREEAM Communities	STAR Community	Green Star Communities
Governance	Built Environment	Governance
Social & Economic Wellbeing	Climate & Energy	Liveability
Resources & Energy	Economy & Jobs	Economic Prosperity
Land use & Ecology	Education, Arts & Community	Environment
Transport & Movement	Equity & Empowerment	Innovation
Innovation	Health & Safety	
	Natural Systems	
	Innovation & Process	

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220 The importance given to the categories forming these systems showed considerable
 221 disparities. Social & Economic Wellbeing is the most awarded category in BREEAM,

222 with 42.7% of the total score. However, the credit Energy Strategy, included in the Re-
223 sources & Energy category, can receive up to 9% of the points. Meanwhile, the score
224 allocated to the categories of Green Star fluctuates between 26% for Environment and
225 19% for Economic Prosperity, although the most valued credit is associated with the De-
226 sign review credit, belonging to the Governance category. Finally, STAR provides equal
227 marks to each category, except for Innovation & Process.

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229 **2.2. Assortment of global actions in the resilience field**

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231 The Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030 (UNISDR, 2015) was
232 adopted in 2015 as the instrument to replace the Hyogo framework (UNISDR, 2005). The
233 new plan identified 7 new global targets and 38 indicators. Four priorities for disaster risk
234 action at all levels were also implemented to facilitate understanding, emphasize the rel-
235 evance of the governance, invest and prepare for an effective response according to the
236 principle of “Build Back Better”. The new scheme also reasserted all the principles in-
237 cluded in the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development of 1992 (UNCED,
238 1992).

239 The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (UN-Habitat, 2015) was enacted in
240 2015 to supersede the UN Millennium Declaration endorsed in 2000. Thus, the former 8
241 Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) were replaced by new 17 SDGs (SDSN, 2015),
242 encompassing 169 targets and 232 indicators to monitor their achievement. Among the
243 SDGs, the transformation of cities into safe, inclusive, resilient and sustainable places for
244 living is addressed by 10 targets and 14 indicators of the SDG#11 (“Sustainable Cities
245 and Communities”) (Table 3), which also attempts to reduce people affected and eco-
246 nomic losses caused by disasters and promote policies and plans according to the Sendai
247 Framework.

Table 3. Targets and indicators of the SDG#11 (SDSN, 2015)

Target	Indicator	Description
11.1.	11.1.1.	Proportion of urban population living in slums, informal settlements or inadequate housing
11.2.	11.2.1.	Proportion of population that has convenient access to public transport
11.3.	11.3.1.	Ratio of land consumption rate to population growth rate
	11.3.2.	Proportion of cities with a direct participation structure of civil society in urban planning and management
11.4.	11.4.1.	Total expenditure (public and private) per capita spent on the preservation, protection and conservation of all cultural and natural heritage
11.5.	11.5.2.	Direct disaster economic loss in relation to global GDP, including disaster damage to critical infrastructure and disruption of basic services
11.6.	11.6.1.	Proportion of urban solid waste regularly collected
	11.6.2.	Annual mean levels of fine particulate matter (e.g. PM2.5 and PM10)
11.7.	11.7.1.	Average share of the built-up area of cities that is open space for public use
	11.7.2.	Proportion of persons victim of physical or sexual harassment
11.A.	11.A.1.	Proportion of population living in cities that implement urban and regional development plans
11.B.	11.B.1.	Proportion of local governments that adopt and implement local disaster risk reduction strategies in line with the Sendai Framework
	11.B.2.	Number of countries with national and local disaster risk reduction strategies
11.C.	11.C.1.	Proportion of financial support to the least developed countries

2.3. Identification of major resilience frameworks

During the last years, diverse tools and methods have been developed to appraise resilience in the urban realm, inter alia, the Geospatial Risk and Resilience Assessment Platform (EU, 2015), the Communities Advancing Resilience Toolkit (Pfefferbaum et al., 2013), the Baseline Resilience Indicators for Communities (Cutter et al., 2010), the Resilience Matrix (Fox-Lent et al., 2015) or some frameworks devised by the US National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST, 2018). However, none of them is widely used worldwide and they all analyze resilience aspects only partially. Instead, the City Resilience Index (CRI), the City Resilience Profiling Tool (CRPT) emerged as indicator systems of urban risk and resilience powered by the following entities: the Earthquakes and Megacities Initiative, the Framework for Community Resilience, the Grosvenor Resilient Cities approach, the ICLEI Asian Cities Climate Change Resilient Network (ACCCRN) Process, the Community-Based Resilience Analysis (CoBRA) Conceptual Framework and the Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities.

The Rockefeller Foundation and Arup built the CRI to evaluate diverse factors that affect the resilience of cities (Arup, 2015). The tool was adopted by the 100 Resilient Cities initiative to guide the development of city resilience strategies embracing social, economic and environmental aspects across the world (Rockefeller Foundation, 2013). As represented in Table 4, the index comprises 4 dimensions and 5 key goals. Furthermore, every CRI element includes the seven qualities of resilient systems determined by

271 Arup, namely Flexible, Redundant, Robust, Resourceful, Reflective, Inclusive and Inte-
 272 grated. A set of questions are undertaken to measure the 52 indicators forming the index.
 273 The achievable scores are classified into 5 categories: Excellent, Good, Moderate, Poor
 274 and Very Poor.

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Table 4. City Resilience Index (Arup, 2015)

Dimensions	Goals	Qualities
Leadership and strategy	Effective leadership and management	Flexible
Health and wellbeing	Empowered stakeholders	Redundant
Economy and society	Integrated development planning	Robust
Infrastructure and ecosystems	Minimal human vulnerability	Resourceful
	Diverse livelihoods and employment	Reflective
		Inclusive
		Integrated

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The search for making cities safer places to live and work is the primary objective of the City Resilience Profiling Programme (CRPP) (UN-Habitat, 2012) launched in 2012 by UN-Habitat. This initiative establishes four accomplishments aimed at building a flexible urban framework for any human settlement, producing metrics for calibrating urban systems, developing software tools and preparing global standards. The CRPT was presented in 2013 as a self-assessment tool to support the implementation of the CRPP. The CRPT was fully updated in 2017 to incorporate mandates and resolutions adopted by the international community, such as the SDGs, the New Urban Agenda, the Paris Agreement for Climate Change and the Sendai Conference (UN-Habitat, 2017). The city resilience profile is drawn by collecting data grouped into 4 SETs: City ID, Local Governments & Stakeholders, Shocks, Stresses & Challenges and Urban Elements. These SETs encompass 19 key analytical functions and 60 sub-functions. SET₁ provides a static view of cities by gathering information about their development, including history, spatial context, local government, demography and economy. The characterization of local government and public administrations and the identification of stakeholders and their relationships are the aim of SET₂. The determination of stresses and shocks that can affect cities, as well as the measures addressed to reduce vulnerability and risk are evaluated by SET₃. Lastly, SET₄ includes diverse factors affecting the urban framework, such as built environment, supply chain & logistics, basic infrastructure, mobility, municipal public services, social inclusion & protection, economy and ecology.

The Earthquakes and Megacities Initiative launched a toolkit comprising the Urban Disaster Risk Index, the Risk Management Index and the Disaster Resilience Index to harness the vast experience of their authors (Khazai et al., 2015) in the urban environment. Whilst the former assesses physical damages of buildings and infrastructure, the latter evaluates and monitors the progress of the implementation of policies and processes focused on risk reduction and increasing resilience. Furthermore, the Risk Management Index appraises actions to reduce risk, prepare for crisis and recover from disasters.

305 The Framework for Community Resilience was developed by the International Fed-
306 eration of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC) in 2014, guided by its 2020
307 Strategy oriented to face the major humanitarian and development challenges of this dec-
308 ade. In this vein, the tool aims at contributing to strengthening resilient communities by
309 measuring the effects of IFRC disaster response and early recovery programs. A set of 81
310 indicators are grouped into six categories, namely Improve the knowledge and health of
311 communities, Strengthen the social cohesion of communities, Develop well-maintained
312 and accessible infrastructure and services in communities, Provide economic opportuni-
313 ties to community people, Manage natural assets and Strengthen the connectedness of
314 communities (IFRC, 2014).

315 The Grosvenor Resilient Cities approach was presented in 2014 to rank 50 important
316 cities concentrating in terms of real estate business according to three aspects: Vulnera-
317 bility, Adaptive Capacity and Resilience. Climate, Environment, Resource, Infrastructure
318 and Community are the five dimensions covered by Vulnerability, whilst Adaptive Ca-
319 pacity evaluates five key themes such as Governance, Institutions, Technical & Learning,
320 Planning Systems and Funding Stresses. An average of both aspects serves to measure
321 Resilience (Grosvenor, 2014).

322 The ICLEI ACCCRN Process was developed in 2014 by ICLEI - Local Governments
323 for Sustainability (South Asia & Oceania offices) and the ACCCRN program supported
324 by the Rockefeller Foundation. Experiences from ten ACCCRN cities, namely Indore,
325 Gorakhpur and Surat in India, Bandar Lampung and Semarang in Indonesia, Chiang Rai
326 and Hat Yai in Thailand and Can Tho, Da Nang and Quy Nhon in Vietnam are the basis
327 of this toolkit, which seeks the assessment of climate risks in urban areas to propose effi-
328 cient resilience strategies. Engagement, Climate Research and Impacts Assessment, Vul-
329 nerabilities Assessment and City Resilience Strategy are the four phases of the program.
330 Two further stages are under development to implement and monitor the four previous
331 ones. Three Indian cities contributed to test the toolkit (Gawler and Tiwari, 2014).

332 CoBRA was launched in 2014 as a result of the collaboration between the European
333 Commission and the UNDP Drylands Development Centre, which developed a robust
334 analytical tool able to measure resilience at community and household levels in the con-
335 text of humanitarian interventions for drought in the horn of Africa. The reduction of
336 drought/disaster risks and the improvement of human livelihoods in disaster-prone com-
337 munities are the main goals of this framework, which assesses five dimensions such as
338 Physical, Human, Financial, Natural and Social through 30 indicators (UNDP, 2014).

339 The United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction presented in 2017 the Disaster
340 Resilience Scorecard for Cities as a technical guidance to monitor progress in the achieve-
341 ment of goals defined by the Sendai framework. Ten Essentials for Making Cities Resil-
342 ient structure the scorecard. Governance and Financial Capacity are covered by Essentials
343 1-3, whilst Planning and Disaster Preparation are the aim of Essentials 4-8. Disaster Re-
344 sponse and Recovery are reviewed by Essentials 9-10 (UNISDR, 2017b).

345 Global implementation, the consideration of multiple risk disasters and a clear urban
 346 resilience assessment-orientation were the criteria established to shortlist the frameworks
 347 to be deemed in this research. [Table 5](#) summarizes the main information related to the
 348 selection process.

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350 **Table 5.** Features of global resilience assessment frameworks ([Arup, 2015](#); [Gawler and Tiwari, 2014](#);
 351 [Grosvenor, 2014](#); [IFRC, 2014](#); [Khazai et al., 2015](#); [UNDP, 2014](#); [UN-Habitat, 2017](#); [UNISDR, 2017b](#))

Tool	Year	Focus	Risk	Implementation
CRI	2015	Global	Multiple	Global
CRPT	2017	Global	Multiple	Global
Urban Risk & Resilience	2015	Global	Multiple	India, Jordan, the Philippines
Framework for Community Resilience	2014	Global	Multiple	IFCR projects
Grosvenor Resilient Cities	2014	50 cities	Multiple	50 cities worldwide
ICLEI-ACCCRN Process	2014	Global	Natural	India, Indonesia, Bangladesh, the Philippines
CoBRA	2014	Africa	Drought	Kenya, Uganda, Ethiopia
Disaster Resilience Scorecard	2017	Global	Multiple	Global

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353 CoBRA was designed to be employed in a small number of African countries that
 354 suffer from prolonged drought episodes. The Framework for Community Resilience only
 355 evaluates the influence of IFRC actions in terms of response and recovery after disaster
 356 events. Furthermore, the Grosvenor tool was created to rank 50 selected cities of great
 357 interest for the international real estate sector in terms of resilience capacity. Despite the
 358 Urban Disaster Risk Index, the Risk Management Index and the Disaster Resilience Index
 359 were conceived to be employed worldwide, their degree of implementation is actually
 360 confined to three countries. Moreover, the lack of a single index that merges all these
 361 three metrics hinders the holistic assessment of urban resilience. Similarly, the ICLEI-
 362 ACCCRN process, designed on the basis of the experience of Asian cities facing natural
 363 risks, was only used in cities of four countries. The Disaster Resilience Scorecard ap-
 364 praises the attainment of goals included in the Sendai framework instead of assessing
 365 resilience of urban areas. Hence, the CRI and the CRPT were the selected tools consider
 366 multiple risks, reflect an international deployment and are firmly oriented to the urban
 367 resilience assessment.

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369 **3. Evaluation of sustainable community frameworks**

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371 The analysis undertaken in this section encompasses three different stages, as shown
 372 in [Figure 1](#). Initially, the frameworks were appraised according to the features inherent
 373 to resilience, namely Preparedness & Plan, Absorption, Recovery and Adaptation. Sub-
 374 subsequently, the indicators of the rating systems were benchmarked against the Sendai
 375 Framework and the SDG#11 in the second phase, whilst the CRI and the CRPT were used
 376 as references in the comparison undertaken in the last step.

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378 **3.1. Alignment with resilience features**

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381 According to the definition of resilience settled by the US National Academy of Sci-
 382 ences (NAS, 2012), some temporal phases were determined to characterize the resilience
 of systems, such as Preparedness & Planning, Absorption, Recovery and Adaptation.

383 These stages are associated with a set of common features of resilience, such as Critical
 384 functions, Thresholds, Time-scale and Lessons learned (Connelly et al., 2017). The re-

385 sponsiveness of critical services in case of an adverse event ascertains the evaluation of
 386 systems. Thus, the identification of essential functions involving stakeholders and users

387 (Cumming et al., 2006) is highly necessary for assessing resilience during the phases of
 388 preparation and planning. In order to prevent from a disruptive event, systems are able to

389 absorb a certain level of disturbance without exceeding a previous threshold. When the
 390 limit is crossed, time to recover critical functionality is a major resilience feature to be

391 considered. Lastly, lessons learned from previous disruptions and system response help
 392 enhancing the resilience of systems. Table 6 illustrates all the resilience features identified

393 in the selected community tools. Urban resilience issues were almost omitted by the three
 394 rating systems, with the exception of a few credits involving flood risk assessment &

395 management in BREEAM (2 credits), emergency management & response in STAR (1
 396 credit) and adaptation and resilience (1 credit) in the governance category of Green Star.

397

398

Table 6. Resilience features of community rating systems

Resilience Definition	Resilience Feature	BREEAM Communities	STAR Community	Green Star Communities
Preparedness & Planning	Critical Functions	✓	✓	✗
Absorption	Thresholds	✗	✗	✗
Recovery	Time	✗	✓	✗
Adaptation	Lessons Learned	✗	✗	✓

399

✓ There is correspondence; ✗ There is no correspondence

400

401

3.2. Assessment according to the Sendai Framework

402

403

404 The review of the 40, 49 and 33 credits included in the BREEAM, STAR and Green
 405 Star Communities frameworks, respectively, showed that none of them could be allocated
 to any of the 38 indicators considered by the Sendai Framework due to the markedly

406 statistical nature of the latter. Whilst the indicators contained in global targets from A to
 407 D of the Sendai Framework focus on the appraisal of losses and casualties derived from

408 disasters, those of targets from E to G are primarily related to governance matters. Instead,
 409 the social, economic and environmental issues covered by sustainable urban development

410

were omitted.

411 The lack of correlation between the indicators of the Sendai Framework and the cred-
 412 its considered by the rating systems lies on their different stage of application. Sustaina-
 413 bility score tools were mainly designed to be implemented during the planning and exe-
 414 cution phases of projects; however, the Sendai Framework was mostly conceived to eval-
 415 uate damages derived from the occurrence of disasters in completed projects.

416

417 **3.3. Analysis under the SDG#11 “Sustainable Cities and Communities”**

418

419 As reflected in [Table 7](#), the credits in BREEAM Communities, STAR and Green Star
 420 Communities were grouped according to their correspondence with the SDG#11 indica-
 421 tors. Moreover, the different components of the three sustainability tools were also dis-
 422 tributed among their own sections, as shown in [Figure 2](#). Whilst 60% of the BREEAM
 423 indicators were assigned to the SDG#11 indicators, less than one third of the STAR and
 424 Green Star credits were consistent with them. The BREEAM system did not provide any
 425 indicators matching 11.5.2., 11.6.1., 11.6.2. and 11.7.2 ([Table 3](#)). Furthermore, some
 426 credits of the STAR and Green Star tools were not aligned with several SDG#11 indica-
 427 tors, such as 11.1.1., 11.2.1., 11.5.2., 11.6.2., 11.7.1., 11.B.2. and 11.C.1 ([Table 3](#)). The
 428 proportion of global GDP related to direct disaster economic loss (11.5.2.) was not asso-
 429 ciated with any component of the assessed frameworks.

430

431

Table 7. Alignment between the community frameworks’ credits and the SDG#11 indicators

SDG#11 Indicator	BREEAM Communities	STAR Community	Green Star Communities
11.1.1.	SE05	BE4	
11.2.1.	TM01, TM04, TM06	BE7	
11.3.1.	LE02	NS6	GOV2
11.3.2.	GO01, GO02, GO03, GO04	EAC1, EE1	GOV7
11.4.1.	SE14	EAC4	LIV4
11.5.2.			
11.6.1.		CE7	ENV7
11.6.2.		NS4	
11.7.1.	SE07, SE11, TM02, TM03, TM05	BE3, BE6, EE4, NS1	
11.7.2.			LIV7
11.A.1.	SE02, SE15, SE17	BE5, EJ3	ECON6
11.B.1.	SE10, SE13		GOV4
11.B.2.	SE03	CE1, HS6	
11.C.1.	RE04, RE05, RE06		

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434

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436

437

All the indicators of Governance (GOV) and Transport & Movement (TM) categories in BREEAM were interlinked with SDG#11. In contrast, Land Use & Ecology (LE) only provided 1 match. 10 and 3 out of 17 and 7 credits of the Social & Economic Wellbeing (SE) and Resources & Energy (RE) categories, respectively, agreed with the SDG#11 indicators, as illustrated in [Figure 2a](#). Overall, the STAR and Green Star credits exhibited

438 a low level of coincidence with SDG#11 (Figure 2b and c). Except for the Built Environ-
 439 nment (BE) and Natural Systems (NS) sections, the correspondence provided by the re-
 440 maining categories did not reach 50%. The general correlation between the SDG#11 in-
 441 dicators and the Green Star credits was similar. Although the allocation of Liveability
 442 (LIV) credits exceeded 50%, Governance (GOV), Economic prosperity (ECON), Envi-
 443 ronment (ENV) and Innovation (INN) were below this percentage.
 444

445 **Figure 2.** Correspondence per category between the indicators of the community rating systems and the
 446 SDG#11 a) BREEAM Communities b) STAR Community c) Green Star Communities

447
 448 Although making more resilient cities is one of the major goals established by the
 449 SDG#11, only 3 of its 14 indicators cover resilience issues associated with “direct disaster
 450 economic loss in relation to global GDP” (11.5.2.), “proportion of local governments with
 451 disaster risk reduction strategies aligned with the Sendai Framework” (11.B.1.) and “the
 452 number of countries with national and local risk disaster reduction strategies” (11.B.2.).
 453 These metrics are slightly linked with planning and absorption phases; however, the re-
 454 covery and adaptation stages were overlooked. Thus, the SDG#11 offers an incomplete
 455 view of resilience without identifying critical services, setting permissible thresholds,
 456 minimizing disruptive events and learning from past experiences. As reflected in Table
 457 7, the correspondence between the credits of the frameworks and the three SDG#11 indi-
 458 cators connected with resilience is very poor. Whilst 11.5.2. showed no coincidence at

459 all, the two other indicators suggested the liaison between the three rating systems and
460 the adoption and implementation of risk disaster reduction plans at local or national level.

461

462 **3.4. Comparison with the City Resilience Index (CRI)**

463

464 The relationship between the components of the City Resilience Index (CRI) and the
465 three sustainable community rating systems is summarized in [Table 8](#). The coincidence
466 between the CRI and the frameworks was uneven. The credits of STAR Community
467 reached a value over 57%, followed by those of BREEAM and Green Star with 52 and
468 31%, respectively. The largest number of credits associated with Health & Wellbeing and
469 Economy & Society was considered by STAR, whilst BREEAM was the system with
470 more elements in the Infrastructure & Ecosystems and Leadership & Strategy categories.
471 On the contrary, BREEAM was the framework with less elements correlated with the CRI
472 indicators in terms of Health & Wellbeing and Economy & Society. Furthermore, the
473 lowest quantity of credits in the Infrastructure & Ecosystems and Leadership & Strategy
474 aspects was exhibited by Green Star, with 4 and 2 items, respectively.

475 As shown in [Figure 3a](#), over 67% of the elements included in the BREEAM categories
476 were connected with the CRI indicators. Only the Resources & Energy (RE) section
477 lacked common bonds with this initiative. With respect to the STAR system, Built Envi-
478 ronment (BE), Economy & Jobs (EJ), Education, Arts & Community (EAC), Health &
479 Safety (HS) and Natural Systems (NS) had a percentage over 50% in what concerns the
480 assignment of their credits to the CRI elements. Instead, Climate & Energy (CE), Equity
481 & Empowerment (EE) and Innovation & Process (IP) were below this threshold ([Figure](#)
482 [3b](#)). [Figure 3c](#) reflects a low interrelationship among all the credits of the Green Star tool
483 and the CRI indicators (48.48%), although the categories of Governance (GOV), Livea-
484 bility (LIV) and Economic Prosperity (ECON) exceeded a value of coincidence of 50%.

485

Table 8. Correspondence between the indicators of the community frameworks and the CRI

Category	Goal	Indicator	BREEAM	STAR	Green Star
Health & Wellbeing	1.	1.1.	SE05	BE4	
		1.2.	SE06	CE3	ECON2
		1.3.		CE5	
		1.4.		BE2	ENV1
		1.5.		HS4	LIV6
	2.	2.1.		EJ4	
		2.2.		EJ6	ECON3
		2.3.	SE01, SE17	EJ3	ECON6
		2.4.			
		2.5.			
	3.	3.1.		HS5	
		3.2.		HS2	
		3.3.			
		3.4.		HS3	
Economy & Society	4.	4.1.		EAC1	ECON1
		4.2.	TM02, SE15	EAC2	LIV2
		4.3.	SE14	EAC4	LIV4
		4.4.	GO04	EE1	GOV3
	5.	5.1.		HS7	LIV7
		5.2.			
		5.3.			
		5.4.		EE4	
	6.	6.1.			
		6.2.			
6.3.			EJ2		
6.4.			EJ1,EJ5		
Infrastructure & Ecosystems	7.	7.1.	SE03, SE10, SE13	CE1, HS6	GOV4
		7.2.			
		7.3.	LE01, LE03, LE04		GOV8
		7.4.			
	8.	8.1.	LE05	NS2, NS3	ENV6
		8.2.		NS1	
		8.3.	SE07	BE3	
		8.4.	SE09		
		8.5.			
	9.	9.1.	TM01, SE11, TM03, TM04, TM05, TM06	BE7	
		9.2.			
		9.3.			ECON7
		9.4.			

488

Table 8 (Continued)

Category	Goal	Indicator	BREEAM	STAR	Green Star	
Leadership & Strategy	10.	10.1.			GOV7	
		10.2.				
		10.3.	GO01			
		10.4.				
		10.5.				
	11.	11.1.				
		11.2.	GO02			
		11.3.	GO03			
	12.	12.1.				
		12.2.				
		12.3.		LE02	BE5, BE6, NS6	GOV2
		12.4.				

489

490

491

492

Figure 3. Correspondence per category between the indicators of the community rating systems and the CRI a) BREEAM Communities b) STAR Community c) Green Star Communities

493

494

495

Although the CRI scheme encompasses 12 goals monitored by 52 indicators, only 11 of them are related to resilience through the goals #7 (“Reduce Exposure & Fragility”),

496 #8 (“Effective provision of critical services”) and #10 (“Effective Leadership & Manage-
497 ment”). However, the whole resilience life-cycle from Preparedness & Planning to Adap-
498 tion was deemed.

499 The remaining metrics focus on key sustainable matters involving health, affordability
500 of basic supplies, crime, education, economy, transport, local community and municipal
501 government. Thus, the four categories of the CRI, namely Economy & Society, Infra-
502 structure & Ecosystems, Health & Wellbeing and Leadership & Strategy display a pro-
503 portional distribution of indicators with 13, 13, 14 and 12 items, respectively. Neverthe-
504 less, the environmental dimension was only represented by 1 out of 52 indicators, show-
505 ing a huge imbalance towards the remaining sustainability pillars.

506 BREEAM allocated the highest amount of credits to the CRI goals specifically ori-
507 ented to resilience, reaffirming why this system reflects the greatest level of correspond-
508 ence. In contrast, the degree of correlation achieved by STAR and Green Star was about
509 50% of that corresponding to BREEAM.

510

511 **3.5. Benchmarking against the City Resilience Profiling Tool (CRPT)**

512

513 [Table 9](#) contains the linkage among the credits of the three sustainability frameworks
514 and the indicators comprised in the four SETS of the City Resilience Profiling Tool
515 (CRPT). The proportion of allocation fluctuated between 51.52% (Green Star) and
516 71.42% (STAR), with BREEAM accounting for 60% of the items included in the CRPT
517 initiative. Whilst BREEAM addressed the largest group of SET₃ indicators (“Shocks,
518 Stresses and Challenges”), no credits of STAR and Green Star were associated with indi-
519 cators of SET₁ (“City Identification”). The majority of CRPT indicators was concentrated
520 within SET₄ (“Urban Elements”), with the STAR framework showing the highest corre-
521 lation to these aspects.

522 More than 50% of the credits included in the five categories of BREEAM were asso-
523 ciated with CRPT indicators included in SET₄, as reflected in [Figure 4a](#). Among them,
524 Governance (GOV) and Land Use & Ecology (LE) achieved more than 75% of corre-
525 spondence. With the exception of Innovation & Process (IP), all the other STAR catego-
526 ries exceeded a value of 50% of correlation between their indicators and those in the
527 CRPT ([Figure 4b](#)). This percentage reached more than 70% in Built Environment (BE),
528 Climate & Energy (CE), Education, Arts & Community (EAC) and Health & Safety (HS).
529 The Green Star framework followed a similar trend in [Figure 4c](#), whereby the interrelation
530 between all categories and the CRPT indicators ranged from 42.85 to 62.5%.

531

Table 9. Correspondence between the indicators of the community frameworks and the CRPT

SET	Key Analytical Function	BREEAM Communities	STAR Community	Green Star Communities
1.	Historical Context Spatial Context Local Government & Public Administration Population & Demographics Economy & Livelihoods Hazards & Challenges			
2.	Role & Place different public Administrations Stakeholders mapping Stakeholders relationships	GO02	EAC2	
3.	Shocks & External Stresses Internal & Complex Stresses	SE03,SE09,SE13	CE1,HS6	GOV4
4.	Built Environment Supply Chain & Logistics Basic Infrastructure Mobility Municipal Public Services Social Inclusion & Protection Economy Ecology	LE02,GO03, SE02,SE05,SE06 RE01,RE03, LE06,RE06 TM01,TM04, TM06 SE14 GO04,SE17 SE01 LE01,LE04, LE05,RE07	BE3,BE4 CE3 CE4,BE2,CE5, CE7 BE7,NS1 HS3,HS7,EAC1, EAC4,EAC5 EE1,EE4,EE5, EE6,EAC3,HS4, HS5 EJ1,EJ3,EJ5 NS2,NS3,NS4, NS5,NS6,BE1, CE2,CE6	GOV2 LIV6 ENV1,ENV7, ECON7 ENV4 LIV4,LIV7 GOV3,GOV7, ECON4 ECON1,ECON6 ENV2,ENV6, GOV8

Figure 4. Correspondence per category between indicators of the community rating systems and the CRPT a) BREEAM Communities b) STAR Community c) Green Star Communities

The structure of the CRPT, which is grounded on four SETs of metrics providing a comprehensive outline of cities instead of appraising resilience issues in detail, was the justification of its high correspondence with the three community rating frameworks (Table 9). Most of the correlated indicators are concentrated in SET₄ (“Urban Elements”), but a very limited number of indicators are represented in SET₂ (“Local Governments and Stakeholders”) and SET₃ (“Shocks, Stresses and Challenges”). As with the CRI, only 8 of the 60 key analytical functions considered by the CRPT were found to be directly connected with resilience, namely Shocks & External Stress, Built Environment, Basic Infrastructure, Mobility, Municipal Public Services, Social Inclusion & Protection, Economy and Ecology. These links were limited to the Preparedness & Planning and Absorption stages, such that the Recovery and Adaptation phases were discarded.

4. Conclusions

This article appraised the resilient nature of BREEAM, STAR and Green Star Communities rating systems through the review of core existing global resilience efforts, such as the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction, the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) #11 (“Sustainable Cities and Communities”), the City Resilience Index (CRI) and

555 the City Resilience Profiling Tool (CRPT). Furthermore, the community frameworks
 556 were analyzed through the prism of the phases associated to resilience, such as Prepared-
 557 ness, Planning, Absorption, Recovery and Adaptation. The main conclusions drawn from
 558 this investigation are as follows:

- 559 • Resilience and sustainability are complementary properties necessary to jointly en-
 560 hance urban development.
- 561 • Neither the Sendai Framework nor the SDG#11 are adequate instruments to evaluate
 562 urban resilience issues. Whilst the former is mainly oriented to quantify impacts of
 563 hazards after their occurrence, without covering prominent aspects of resilience re-
 564 lated to prepare, plan for, recover from and adapt to adverse events, the latter shows
 565 major gaps to gauge the resilience phases mentioned above.
- 566 • The CRI emerges as the most comprehensive initiative to assess the degree of resili-
 567 ence of urban communities throughout all its phases, despite most of its indicators are
 568 related to sustainability concerns instead of expanding and deepening resilience is-
 569 sues. In contrast, the CRPT, which shows a scarce coverage of environmental issues,
 570 is primarily focused on determining city profiles to evaluate urban systems, instead of
 571 assessing their recovery capability.
- 572 • The CRPT displayed the greatest level of correspondence with the indicators of the
 573 three community systems, with STAR being the framework that reflected the highest
 574 amount of credits allocated to the CRPT. Moreover, BREEAM was the most suitable
 575 for SDG#11 and the CRI. Green Star revealed a very poor alignment with the two
 576 global initiatives taken as benchmarks.

577 On the whole, all three community systems disclosed multiple and prominent gaps,
 578 thus hindering the accurate evaluation of resilience in urban communities. Due to the
 579 intimate connection between sustainability and resilience, the development of a new
 580 framework focused on urban areas considering both matters is highly suggested to cover
 581 all the resilience stages, with emphasis on highlighting the recovery and adaptation
 582 phases.

583

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